

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842
ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue I, January 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678 / Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

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ISSN (Online) 2799-0842
ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

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Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024) / International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678 / Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Leadership Practices of School Heads and Their Effects on School-Based Management Performance

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Abstract

School-Based Management (SBM) is a child and community-centered education system based on the RA 9155-Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, Schools First Initiative (SFI 2005), and Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA, 2006). The Department of Education (DepEd) has been working to develop activities and programs that promote strong leadership and decision-making for all members of the school community. School heads play a significant role in regulating decisions within schools, affecting the structure of school employees and curriculum competencies. This study applied the descriptive-correlational method of research to determine the relationship between the school profile and the level of management practices of school heads as perceived by respondents. The researcher used standardized questionnaires as primary data gathering techniques and conducted a null hypothesis test at the significance level of 0.05. The results were processed using the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) and analyzed using statistical tests such as multiple correlations and regression analysis to determine the effects of school heads' leadership practice on SBM practice. The findings highlight the importance of fostering a collaborative environment within the school premises and promoting effective school management practices.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10458935

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